

INTEGRATING TED TALKS IN ELT: A TBLT APPROACH TO ENHANCE SPEAKING AND LISTENING SKILLS FROM TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

The present research explores the impact of TED talks on English language teaching and highlights the hurdles teachers often face while integrating TED talks in ELT classrooms. A mixed approach was used in this study. The population of the study comprises teachers from three Pakistani universities. A sample size of 30 participants was selected equally from these universities through random sampling. An online questionnaire was used as a research instrument for purposive data collection. The questionnaire was contained in three parts the first part comprises demographic information of the research participants, the second part includes fifteen close-ended questions to find the answer to the first research question, and the third part contains one open-ended question to find the answer to a second research question. The questionnaire was sent to the research contributors via WhatsApp and emails. The data was collected and congregated data was later analyzed by using SPSS latest version 24. The data was presented in the figures and tables in numerical form. The research findings revealed that TED talks in ELT classrooms improve students' speaking, and listening skills, increase student engagement, and expose diverse topics and authentic language. Moreover, the research findings also highlighted some hurdles while integrating TED talks in ELT classrooms. Based on these findings researcher presented some recommendations for future researchers.

Keywords: ELT classrooms, task-based learning, listening skills, speaking skills, and teachers' perspectives.

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, technology pervades all aspects of life, including education, Maitlo et al. (2024; Kalhor, et al., 2023). This technological advancement provides readily

accessible learning resources anytime and anywhere. The integration of informative, engaging, and inspiring media into the task-based language teaching process offers numerous

advantages. Media use is intrinsically linked to language use, as it can significantly facilitate language acquisition. Language itself is fundamental for global communication, allowing individuals to express their thoughts, feelings, and aspirations through both verbal and non-verbal means. TED serves as a prominent example of an open-access platform for teaching and learning. TED Talks provide a valuable resource for English language teachers and learners (Ziebell, 2019). These engaging and readily available talks can enhance classroom instruction and encourage students to express themselves in English. Ziebell (2019) highlights their suitability for a CLIL-like approach in ESL teaching, emphasizing their potential to spark student interest. The nonprofit organization TED focuses on sharing powerful ideas through concise speeches covering a wide range of topics, from technology and science to personal growth and the environment. With over 3100 talks available, teachers can easily find inspiring content to cater to individual student interests.

TED, an educational media organization, hosts global conferences and events. Their signature presentations, known as TED Talks, are available as videos on the TED website, offering anytime, anywhere access (Amalia, 2020).

TED, an acronym for "Technology, Entertainment, and Design" (DeCesare, 2014), is a nonprofit dedicated to disseminating ideas through concise and impactful talks, typically under 18 minutes in length (Maser, 2021). These talks cover a diverse range of subjects, from entertainment to language teaching.

TED Talks, a division of TED, present "constrained" presentations, often resulting in more inspiring, creative, and engaging content (Gallo, 2014). The researcher's interest in reviewing prior studies on TED Talks in English Language Teaching (ELT) has led to the following research objectives: to examine the use of TED Talks in ELT based on previous related studies. TED Talks, originating from 1984, have become a valuable resource in contemporary English Language Teaching (ELT) classrooms. With over 1800 talks and 35,000 transcripts available online (Salem, 2019), they offer a rich source of intellectually stimulating content.

Integrating TED Talks into ELT classrooms provides numerous benefits for both teachers and learners. Effective implementation involves creating lessons around TED Talk videos or Ed-Animations, sharing these online, and tracking student progress. TED Talks effectively enhance English language skills, particularly speaking, writing, listening, and reading. Their value lies in their accessibility and the wealth of knowledge they offer. This study aims to investigate the impact of TED Talks in ELT while also identifying and addressing the challenges teachers often encounter when integrating them into their classrooms.

Statement of Problem

A statement of the problem is a clear and concise summary of the research problem, usually contained in a single passage and its role is to recognize the concerned problem (Ahmad et al., 2021; Ahmad, Farhat & Abbas, 2024). TED Talks is a new approach to English language teaching that can improve students' English language skills. TED Talks is already used by some teachers, while most have not used it, only heard about it. In Pakistan, only a few teachers are using this approach for language teaching. The present research is worthy because it grabs its worth through this survey research. In many countries, the TED Talks approach is integrated into learning, but in Pakistan, it is used on a small scale; consequently, most educators are unaware of its beneficial results. The researcher conducts this research to highlight its position through a survey. Although this tool is helping in language teaching teachers face various kinds of hurdles while integrating TED Talks in classrooms.

Significance of Study

- The present research will be beneficial not only in English Language learning but it will be also advantageous for the teachers and students of other departments.
- The study will instigate the researchers and scholars to research more and more about the usage and effect of this approach which was disregarded for a long time in Pakistan.
- The present research will benefit the upcoming researchers and scholars in directing their research

work to the related topic and will be supportive in overcoming hurdles.

Research Questions

- How do TED Talks impact listening, speaking, and interaction skills in ELT classrooms?
- What hurdles are faced by teachers while integrating TED Talks in ELT classrooms?

Objectives

- To access the TED Talks impacts listening, speaking, and interaction skills in ELT classrooms.
- To identify the hurdles faced by the teachers while integrating TED Talks in ELT classrooms.

Research Limitations

- The research is limited only to the teachers' perceptions of sidestepping students.
- Population is limited to English department teachers of three universities.
- Sampling is also limited only to 30 teachers.
- Sample size is also limited to fifteen closed-ended questions and one open-ended question.

Literature Review

Salem, (2019; Jeevan, et al., 2023) tried to explore the effect of TED Talks on improving oral presentation skill vocabulary retention and its impact on reducing speaking anxiety. The mixed method is used in the research, which includes both quantitative and qualitative data collecting and analyzing processes Amin, et al., (2023). For this quasi-experimental research, 49 students were selected from the Sadat Academy of Management Sciences in Egypt. These students were studying English subject to prepare themselves for banks and accounting jobs. At the time of the experiment, their English skill level was equal to the IELTS 5.5 band. The participants were divided into two groups experimental contain on 24 and control on 25 students. The results of the study exposed that TED Talks as an ICT instrument has improved the student's oral presentation skills.

Kozinska, (2021; Maitlo, et al., 2022) examined the resources which are developing listening, speaking, and interaction skills in teaching EFL to university students through TED Talks resources. The population of the study was the third-year students of International Economic Relations studying English subject. The 50 participants were

selected for sampling to contribute to this research, but only 27 students and five teachers' responded questionnaire. The results revealed that TED Talks is a beneficial and supporting tool for English language learners.

Maharani et al, (2023; Cheema, et al., 2023; Ahmad, et al., 2022) investigated the impact of TED Talks video-based material for enhancing students' listening skills. The research is quasi-experimental and conducted in the Iranian context. The 60 Iranian intermediate-level male EFL learners were selected as research participants. These participants were divided into three groups and taught by employing different approaches. The results revealed that the students taught using TED Talks video-based material performed better than the other two approaches.

Tran & Nguyen, (2024; Ahmad, et al., 2023) used TED Talks to enhance students' public speaking skills. The study investigated how the Van Lang University EFL students use TED Talks to improve their public speaking skills. A mixed method (quantitative and qualitative) was used in this research. The population of the research was students of Van Lang University. A sample of 61v students was selected by using a purposive sampling technique. An online questionnaire was sent to these participants for data collection. The questionnaire contained three parts, the first part comprised demographic information, the second part contained 14, and the third part contained 16 questions. The data was collected and analyzed through SPSS. The results revealed that TED Talks are refining students' public speaking skills.

Some more research on TED Talks is as:

- Karunakar, (2019), Encouraging English language production using TED talks at the tertiary level: a study in a technical college.
- Mojgan & Tollabi, (2019), Exploring Iranian EFL learners' listening skills via TED talks: does the medium make a difference?
- Tatyana, (2021). The advantages of using TED Talks materials in ESL classrooms.

However, in the Pakistani context there is not much work done on this approach, so the researcher tried to fill this gap by using the following methodology.

Research Methodology

This research employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection methods Ahmad, et al., (2023). The study comprised three distinct stages: firstly, a close-ended questionnaire was developed to gather data from 30 participants in the English Language Departments. Secondly, an open-ended questionnaire was designed to delve deeper into the participants' perspectives and experiences. Lastly, Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key informants. Selection criteria for interviewees were based on their expertise and experience in English Language Teaching and the use of technology in education.

Research Sample: The population of the present research study comprises ESL teachers of the English department of three universities. A sample of thirty ESL teachers was selected by using a random sampling technique. The

participants were selected equally from three universities.

Research Instrument: An online questionnaire was used for data collection as a research tool. The questionnaire contains two parts, part A comprises demographic information of the participants, part B contains fifteen close-ended questions and Part C contains one open-ended question.

Data Collection & Analysis Process: The questionnaire was sent to the teachers of this university through WhatsApp and Emails for data collection. The collected data was later analyzed by using the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 2024. The analyzed data was presented in figures and tables in numerical form.

Demographic statistics

Demographic information of the research participants is presented in the following figure.

Figure: 01: Demographic information of the research participants

Figure number one shows that there were a total of thirty research participants selected equally from the three Pakistani universities.

inquired one open-ended question from the research contributors. The results of these close-ended and open-ended questions are presented below in the tables.

Results

To find the answer to the first research question researcher asked fifteen close-ended questions from the research contributors. To find the answer to the second research question the researcher

Section I: Close-Ended Question

This part of the research contains fifteen close-ended questions, five on listening, five on speaking, and five on interaction skills.

Listening Skill

Table: 01: Do You Think Integration of TED Talks in ELT Foster Listening Skill?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	9	10.6%	10.6%	10.6%
	Agree	12	14.1%	14.1%	24.7%
	Neutral	1	1.2%	1.2%	25.9%

Disagree	5	5.9%	5.9%	31.8%
Strongly disagree	3	3.5%	3.5%	35%
Total	30	100%	100%	100%

Strongly agreed: frequency 9, percent & valid percent 10.6%, and cumulative percent 10.6%. Agreed: frequency 12, percent and valid percentage 14.1%, and cumulative percentage 24.7%. Neutral: frequency 1, percent and valid percent 1.2%, and cumulative percent 25.9%.

Disagreed: frequency 5, percent and valid percent 5.9%, and cumulative percentage 35%. Strongly disagreed: frequency 3, percent and valid percent 3.5%, and cumulative percentage 11.8%. Total: frequency 30, percent & valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 02: Do You Think Integration of TED Talks Improves Teacher's Listening Skills?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	19	22.4%	22.4%	22.4%
	No	11	12.9%	12.9%	35.3%
Total		30	100%	100%	100%

In the above table frequency 19, percent and valid percent 22.4%, and cumulative Percent 22.4%. Frequency 10, percent and valid percent 12.9%,

and cumulative Percent 35.3%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative Percent 100%.

Table: 03: Do You Think Integration of TED Talks Improves Student's Listening Skills?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	23	27.1%	27.1%	27.1%
	No	7	8.2%	8.2%	35.3%
Total		30	100%	100%	100%

Frequency 23, percent and valid percent 27.1%, and cumulative percent 27.1%. Frequency 7, percent and valid percentage 8.2%, and

cumulative percent 35.3%. Frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 04: Do You Think the TED Talks tool must be used to improve Listening Skills?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	18	21.2%	21.2%	21.2%
	No	12	14.1%	14.1%	35.3%
Total		30	100%	100%	100%

Frequency 18, percent and valid percent 21.2%, and cumulative percent 21.2%. Frequency 12, percent and valid percent 14.1%, and cumulative

percent 35.3%. Frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 05: Do You Think Due to TED Talks Tool Learner Listen Attentively?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	21	24.7%	24.7%	24.7%
	No	9	10.6%	10.6%	35.3%
Total		30	100%	100%	100%

Frequency 21, percent and valid percentage 24.7%, and cumulative percentage 24.7%. Frequency 9, percent and valid percentage 10.6%,

and cumulative percent 35.3%. Frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Speaking Skill

Table: 06: Do You Think Integration of TED Talks in ELT Improves Speaking Skill?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	11	12.9%	12.9%	12.9%
	Agree	14	16.5%	16.5%	29.4%
	Neutral	2	2.4%	2.4%	31.8%
	Disagree	2	2.4%	2.4%	34.1%
	Strongly disagree	1	1.2%	1.2%	35%
	Total	30	100%	100%	100%

Strongly agreed: frequency 11, percent and valid percentage 12.9%, and cumulative percentage 12.9%. Agreed: frequency 14, percent and valid percentage 16.5%, and cumulative percentage 29.4%. Neutral: frequency 2, percent and valid percent 2.4%, and cumulative percent 31.8%.

Disagreed: frequency 2, percent and valid percent 2.4%, and cumulative percent 34.1%. Strongly disagreed: frequency 1, percent and valid percent 1.2%, and cumulative percent 35%. Total: frequency 30, percent & valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 07: Integration of TED Talks in ELT Improve Teachers Speaking Skills?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	17	20.0%	20.0%	20.0%
	No	13	15.3%	15.3%	35.3%
	Total	30	100%	100%	100%

Yes: frequency 17, percent and valid percent 20.0%, and cumulative percent 20.0%. No: frequency 10, percent and valid percent 15.3%,

and cumulative percentage 35.3%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 08: Integration of TED Talks in ELT Improve Students Speaking Skills?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	24	28.2%	28.2%	28.2%
	No	6	7.1%	7.1%	35.3%
	Total	30	100%	100%	100%

Yes: frequency 24, percent and valid percentage 28.2%, and cumulative percentage 28.2%. No: frequency 6, percent and valid percent 7.1%, and

cumulative percent 35.3%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 09: TED Talks is the Best Tool for Improving Speaking Skills?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	25	29.4%	29.4%	29.4%
	No	5	5.9%	5.9%	35.3%
	Total	30	100%	100%	100%

Yes: frequency 25, percent and valid percent 29.4%, and cumulative percent 29.4%. No: frequency 5, percent and valid percent 5.9%, and

cumulative percent 35.3%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 10: TED Talks Tool Must be Used in ELT by Teachers to Improve Speaking Skill?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	24	28.2%	28.2%	28.2%
	No	7	8.2%	8.2%	36.5%

Total	30	100%	100%	100%
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Yes: frequency 24, percent and valid percentage 28.2%, and cumulative percentage 28.2%. No: frequency 7, percent and valid percent 8.2%, and cumulative percent 36.5%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Interaction Skill

Table: 11: Do You Think Integration of TED Talks in ELT Improves Interaction Skill?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	8	9.4%	9.4%	9.4%
	Agree	15	17.6%	17.6%	27.1%
	Neutral	0	0.0%	0.0%	27.1%
	Disagree	4	4.7%	4.7%	31.8%
	Strongly disagree	3	3.5%	3.5%	35%
Total		30	100%	100%	100%

Strongly agreed: frequency 8, percent and valid percent 9.4%, and cumulative percentage 9.4%. Agreed: frequency 15, percent and valid percentage 17.6%, and cumulative percentage 27.1%. Neutral: frequency 0, percent and valid percent 0.0%, and cumulative percent 27.1%. Disagreed: frequency 4, percent and valid percent 4.7%, and cumulative percentage 31.8%. Strongly disagreed: frequency 3, percent and valid percent 3.5%, and cumulative percentage 35%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 12: Integration of TED Talks in ELT Increase Student's Engagement in Interaction Skills?

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	24	28.2%	28.2%	28.2%
	No	6	7.1%	7.1%	35.3%
Total		30	100%	100%	100%

Yes: frequency 24, percent and valid percentage 28.2%, and cumulative percentage 28.2%. No: frequency 6, percent & valid percent 7.1%, and cumulative percent 35.3%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 13: Integration of TED Talks in ELT Expose Diverse Topics to Improve Interaction Skills.

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	21	24.7%	24.7%	24.7%
	No	9	10.6%	10.6%	35.3%
Total		30	100%	100%	100%

Yes: frequency 21, percent and valid percentage 24.7%, and cumulative percentage 24.7%. No: frequency 9, percent and valid percent 10.6%, and cumulative percent 35.3%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 14: TED Talks in ELT Expose Authentic Language to Improve Interaction Skills.

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	22	25.9%	25.9%	25.9%
	No	8	9.4%	9.4%	35.3%
Total		30	100%	100%	100%

Yes: frequency 22, percent and valid percent 25.9%, and cumulative percent 25.9%. No: frequency 8, percent and valid percent 9.4%, and cumulative percent 35.3%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Table: 15: TED Talks is Better for Both Teachers and Students for Interaction Skill Improvement.

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	20	23.5%	23.5%	23.5%
	No	10	11.8%	11.8%	35.3%
Total		30	100%	100%	100%

Yes: frequency 20, percent and valid percent 23.5%, and cumulative percent 23.5%. No: frequency 10, percent and valid percent 11.8%,

and cumulative percent 35.3%. Total: frequency 30, percent and valid percent 100%, and cumulative percent 100%.

Section II: Open-Ended Question

What Hurdles You Face While Integrating TED Talks in ELT Classroom?

Extracts from Responses	Codes	Main Theme
• Lack of electrical resources.	Resources	Hurdles While Integrating TED Talks in ELT Classroom
• Usage Issues.	Usage is Sues.	
• Student's attitude problem.	Inconvenient.	
• Shortage of time.	Ti Me.	

The participants were asked what kind of hurdles they faced while integrating TED Talks in the ELT classroom. The lack of electrical resources, issues in use, student's attitude, and shortage of time were the major problems highlighted by the research participants.

Discussions

TED Talks can be effectively integrated into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms for various pedagogical purposes (López-Carril et al., 2020). These talks provide free and engaging content that can enhance lessons, pique student interest in language learning, and foster the development of English skills (Ziebell, 2019). TED Talks can be valuable resources for developing a range of student skills (Kusumastuty et al., 2019), particularly in speaking. Effective speaking instruction often begins by exposing students to exemplary models, such as TED Talks, and guiding them to analyze the structure and presentation style of these talks (Newton et al., 2018). To facilitate this, teachers can assign students to watch selected TED Talks outside of class. This pre-viewing allows students to familiarize themselves with the language and content, enabling deeper analysis and discussion within the classroom setting. Ideally, these talks should exemplify key text structures, such as problem-solution, compare-contrast, and cause-effect, providing valuable models for students'

own speaking and presentation skills. The present research was conducted to find the ESL teachers' perceptions about integrating TED Talks in ELT classrooms. To fulfill this purpose, the researcher developed two research questions to investigate the problem. To know the ESL teachers' perceptions about integrating TED Talks in ELT classrooms, the researcher used an online questionnaire containing three parts first part comprises demographic information of the research participants, while second part contains fifteen close-ended questions, and the third part contains one open-ended question. These questions were asked of the thirty participants of the three universities. The results revealed that most of the participants responded positively to the statements, that TED Talks not only foster listening skills but also improve listening skills and enhance interaction. Moreover, it increases student engagement and exposes diverse topics and authentic language. The results also revealed some hurdles faced by these teachers while integrating TED Talks in ELT classrooms. The results of the current study match with the results and findings of some preceding research as; Morgan & Tollabi, (2019) explored EFL learners' listening skills through the TED Talks approach in the context of Iran; and Maharani et al, (2023) also used this approach for improving students listening skills; a similar approach is used for this study. The researchers (Karunakar, 2019; Salem,

2019; Kozińska, 2021; Tran & Nguyen, 2024) used the same approach for their research regarding English language skills. The results of this research partly match the results of the present research.

Conclusion

As a consequence, English language skills have become easy owing to this convenient new approach. The researcher used a quantitative research design; the data was collected from the thirty participants selected equally from three Pakistani universities. An online questionnaire was used as a tool for data collection. The data was analyzed through the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS), and analyzed data was presented in tables in numerical form. The results demonstrated that TED Talks in ELT classrooms performed a significant role in improving listening, speaking, and interaction skills. The results of the present study revealed that the TED Talks approach is beneficial for learning English language skills, and it must be integrated into English language teaching classrooms. Based on these findings researcher presented the following recommendations.

Recommendations

- There is a need for more research concerning this approach so that the teachers and students get knowledge about this approach.
- Educationists must motivate the teachers and students to employ TED talks in ELT classrooms.
- Teachers must learn proper usage of TED talks in ELT classrooms to avoid any kind of usage hurdle.
- There must be a proper arrangement of electricity supply without any interruption and must be arranged substitute resources of electric supply.
- The students must respect and cooperate with their teachers in building the best atmosphere in the classroom.

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